

MultiX: Advancing 6G-RAN through multi-technology, multi-sensor fusion, multi-band and multi-static perception

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Abstract—MultiX integrates sensing and communication in 6G networks through the MultiX Fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN (MP6R) framework, enhancing awareness and adaptability with multi-band, multi-static, and multi-sensor capabilities. Its distributed architecture includes MultiX Perception System (MPS) for sensing, MPRC Controller (MP6RC) for orchestration, and Data Access and Security Hub (DASH) for secure data processing. The Multi-Layer Digital Twin for Industrial Manufacturing showcases its real-time optimization potential, enabling applications like autonomous systems and smart manufacturing.

A unified ISAC framework must support efficient spectrum sharing, real-time processing, and cross-layer data fusion without harming communication performance. AI-driven sensing, edge computing, and dynamic resource allocation will be key to overcoming interoperability challenges. A fully integrated ISAC system would turn wireless networks into perception-aware infrastructures, enabling precise localization, environment-aware communication, and autonomous system coordination.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sensing is becoming essential in next-generation wireless systems, allowing devices to interpret their surroundings using wireless signals instead of dedicated sensors. This enables motion detection, environment mapping, and object tracking, benefiting applications like autonomous systems and smart environments [1].

Future networks will integrate advanced sensing alongside communication, utilizing Multi-RAT sensing to operate across standards like 5G and Wi-Fi. Multiband sensing further enhances perception by combining sub-6 GHz for wide coverage with mmWave and THz bands for high resolution [2]. By merging these techniques, future wireless systems will enable applications such as smart cities, vehicular networks, and industrial automation, shifting networks toward intelligent, context-aware operation.

II. MAIN CHALLENGES ON SENSING

Most ISAC research focuses on a single wireless technology, either within 3GPP networks (e.g., 5G/6G) or non-3GPP standards (e.g., Wi-Fi sensing). While effective, these approaches often operate independently, limiting their potential in heterogeneous environments. Traditional sensing, relying on separate sensors like LiDAR and radar, results in redundant hardware and spectrum use.

The main challenge for ISAC is integrating diverse sensing sources across the entire RAN, from infrastructure to UE, while managing differences in frequency bands, waveforms, and hardware. Ensuring seamless coordination across the RAN stack is essential.

III. MULTIX VISION

The MultiX project [3] seeks to transform the 3GPP RAN system by introducing the MultiX Fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN (MP6R), which integrates advanced sensing with communication to enhance wireless performance and environmental perception. Key components of MP6R include:

- 1) **Multi-Sensor Fusion:** MP6R combines various sensing modalities to enhance situational awareness and environmental mapping. Network-based sensing leverages radio signals for passive and active detection, while radar, LiDAR, and cameras contribute depth and motion data for improved object tracking.
- 2) **Multi-Band Operation:** MP6R spans multiple frequency bands, using sub-6 GHz for broad coverage, mmWave and THz for high-resolution imaging and precise localization, and 7-24 GHz frequencies for a balance between range and resolution.
- 3) **Multi-Static Processing:** Distributed receivers process signals transmitted by one or more network nodes, enabling collaborative sensing. This approach improves passive detection, distributed radar-like perception, and network-assisted object tracking by fusing signals across receivers.
- 4) **Multi-Technology Integration:** MP6R integrates 3GPP and non-3GPP technologies to expand sensing and communication capabilities. It utilizes 5G/6G for joint communication and sensing while incorporating Wi-Fi and other technologies to ensure seamless interoperability.

IV. MULTIX ARCHITECTURE

The MultiX system (see Fig. 1) presents an innovative architectural framework that seamlessly integrates sensing and communication within the 6G RAN. By utilizing multi-band, multi-static, multi-sensor, and multi-technology deployments, MultiX establishes a perception-driven wireless network that extends beyond traditional connectivity. The architecture is built around three key components:

A. MultiX Perception System (MPS):

MPS embeds MultiX sensing functions across various layers of the RAN stack, deploying them at the RU, DU, BS, and even UE levels. It enables joint signal processing across network elements, supporting features like passive radar-like perception, precise localization, and enhanced environmental awareness. By integrating sensing at different RAN nodes, MPS ensures a distributed and flexible operation, optimizing performance across diverse deployment scenarios.

B. MP6R Controller (MP6RC):

As the intelligence hub of MP6R, MP6RC orchestrates sensing and communication functions across the RAN. Its primary roles include:

- 1) **Multi-Technology Coordination:** MP6RC manages the integration of various wireless technologies (5G, 6G, Wi-Fi, and non-terrestrial networks) while tracking the mobility of sensed objects, ensuring seamless operation in heterogeneous environments.
- 2) **Distributed Data Management:** MP6RC interfaces with DASH nodes to oversee multi-sensor data aggregation, processing, and distribution, ensuring network scalability and real-time responsiveness.

C. Data Access and Security Hub (DASH):

DASH is a novel RAN data plane entity responsible for securely aggregating, processing, and exposing multi-sensor data. It acts as a trusted hub for managing diverse sensing information while maintaining privacy, security, and integrity. DASH can be distributed across the data plane for optimized performance and reduced latency. Key functionalities include:

- 1) **Secure storage and access control** for multi-sensor data, ensuring compliance with trust and regulatory standards.
- 2) **Efficient processing and fusion** of heterogeneous sensing data for enhanced perception and decision-making.
- 3) **Dynamic exposure of processed sensing** information to authorized network functions, applications, and external services.

By combining these components, MultiX creates an adaptive RAN where sensing and communication merge, enabling precise localization, wireless optimization, and autonomous network management for 6G.

Fig. 1. MultiX architectural overview.

V. MULTIX PROOF OF CONCEPT

To validate the MultiX architecture, we present the **Multi-Layer Digital Twin for Industrial Manufacturing**, a proof of concept that enhances industrial operations by integrating sensing, communication, and decision-making. The Digital Twin optimizes configurations based on real-time data, improving efficiency and reliability.

It dynamically adjusts wireless networks to ensure stable performance in fluctuating environments, supporting critical applications. Additionally, it fosters human-machine collaboration and leverages autonomous technologies for better productivity and new business models. The DT uses DASH as a hub for aggregating and processing data from various sources, integrating ISAC and other sensors with AI-driven techniques.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

MultiX unifies sensing and communication in 6G, enhancing awareness, localization, and perception. Its architecture—MPS for sensing, MP6RC for orchestration, and DASH for data processing—ensures adaptability. The Digital Twin proof of concept showcases its impact on decision-making and network performance. Future work will refine integration and real-world validation.

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